

Effective delivery of doxorubicin using biologically synthesized gold nanoparticles for cancer therapy[†]

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Abstract : We synthesized gold nanoparticles (AuHS) by a single step reduction of chloroauric acid solution using aqueous leaf extract of *Hibiscus sabdariffa* (HS) plant through an environmental-friendly bio-green approach. The as-synthesized AuHS nanoparticles were thoroughly characterized by several analytical techniques including UV-Visible spectroscopy, DLS, XRD, TEM, XPS and ICP-OES. Cell viability assay revealed that the nanoparticles are highly biocompatible to various normal cells (EA.hy926 and CHO) as well as cancer cells (HCT-15, HeLa, PC3 and A549). The chick embryonic angiogenesis (CEA) assay also supported the biocompatible nature of AuHS nanoparticles. The nanoparticles were found to be stable in different physiological buffer and other solutions, indicating the feasibility of their biological applications. Considering the biocompatibility of AuHS nanoparticles, FDA approved anti-cancer drug doxorubicin (DOX) was conjugated with the nanoparticles to design a drug delivery system (DDS : AuHS-DOX). The administration of AuHS-DOX to different cancer cells (HCT-15, HeLa and PC3) manifested more inhibition of cell proliferation compared to pristine DOX, suggesting the therapeutic efficacy of the DDS. The better therapeutic response of the DDS could be attributed to the enhanced cellular uptake of DOX present in AuHS-DOX compared to free DOX as observed by confocal microscopy. We strongly believe that the biocompatible AuHS nanoparticles could be employed as an effective delivery vehicle for cancer therapy through nanomedicine approach in imminent future.

Keywords : Gold nanoparticles, biosynthesis, green chemistry approach, drug delivery system, nanomedicine, cancer therapy.

Introduction

Nanotechnology, one of the emerging technologies of modern world, exhibits its enormous potential for various biomedical applications including diagnosis and therapy of different diseases such as cancer, cardiovascular diseases, neurodegenerative diseases, diabetes, microbial infection etc.¹⁻⁸. Since past de-

acades, among various nanomaterials, gold nanoparticles got more attention to the researchers for their diverse applications in varied field including sensor, catalysis, electronics as well as disease diagnosis and therapeutics due to several advantages e.g. (i) simple synthesis method, (ii) easier characterization because of their surface plasmon resonance (SPR) band, (iii)

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easier surface modification, (iv) biocompatibility, (v) long historical use of gold in medicine etc.^{2,4,9-12}. Owing to the numerous applications of gold nanoparticles in today's world, it is highly required to design and develop alternative sustainable, eco-friendly, cost-effective process for the fabrication of gold nanoparticles¹²⁻¹⁴. Therefore, scientists are presently highly engaged toward the advancement of bio-green method for the synthesis of low cost biocompatible gold nanoparticles that could be employed for different applications¹⁵⁻²¹. The bio-green routes for the fabrication of gold nanoparticles possess several advantages compared to conventional chemical methods such as single step, fast reaction, environmentally benign, cost effective etc. making it more convenient approach^{22,23}.

In this context, we have developed biologically synthesized highly stable gold nanoparticles (AuHS) through the reduction of chloroauric acid (HAuCl_4) by aqueous leaf extract of *Hibiscus sabdariffa* (HS), followed by their detailed characterization. *In vitro* cell viability assay and *in vivo* chick embryo angiogenesis (CEA) assay revealed the biocompatible nature of as-synthesized nanoparticles which compelled us to design an AuHS nanoparticles based drug delivery system (DDS : AuHS-DOX) containing anti-cancer drug doxorubicin (DOX). The application of the DDS to different cancer cells exhibited more inhibition of cancer cell proliferation compared to free drug, indicating the efficacy of AuHS nanoparticles as a delivery vehicle for cancer therapy. It could be speculated that the biologically synthesized environment-friendly biocompatible AuHS nanoparticles would be a promising candidate for cancer therapeutic applications in forthcoming future.

Experimental

Materials

Tetrachloroauric(III) acid ($\text{HAuCl}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$), 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyl tetrazolium bromide (MTT reagent), doxorubicin (DOX), Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM), Dulbecco's Phosphate Buffer Saline (DPBS) and fetal bovine serum

(FBS) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, USA and used without further purifications. *Hibiscus sabdariffa* leaves were collected from the CSIR-IICT Campus. Different cancer cell lines (HeLa : human cervical cancer cells; PC3 : human prostate cancer cells; A549 : human lung cancer cells) and normal cell line (CHO : Chinese hamster ovarian cell line) were purchased from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC), USA. Human collateral adenocarcinoma cell line (HCT-15) was obtained from NCCS, Pune, India. Additionally, human endothelial somatic hybrid cell line (EA.hy926) were a kind gift from S. Oglesbee, Tissue Culture Facility, University of North Carolina, Lineberger Comprehensive Cancer Center, NC, USA and S. Chatterjee, Anna University – K. B. Chandrasekhar, Chennai, India. The fertilized chicken eggs were purchased from the government poultry station (Directorate of Poultry Research, Hyderabad, Telangana).

Preparation of stock solutions

Initially, 10^{-2} M HAuCl_4 solution was prepared using autoclaved MiliQ water and this stock solution was further used to synthesize gold nanoparticles. Additionally, 1 mg/mL stock solution of doxorubicin (DOX) was prepared in autoclaved MiliQ water. The stock solution of DOX was further diluted for experimental work.

Preparation of HS leaf extract

At first, the green leaves of HS were thoroughly washed using MiliQ water. In order to prepare the stock solution, 105 g of grounded HS leaves were dissolved in 420 mL autoclaved MiliQ water in a beaker. The crude extract was then heated occasionally at 600 W up to 3 h and stirred for overnight at a magnetic stirrer. The crude extract was finally centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 1 h at 20 °C. Finally, the supernatant (150 mL) was collected and stored at -20 °C for synthesis of AuHS nanoparticles.

Bio-synthesis of AuHS nanoparticles

We have fabricated AuHS nanoparticles through the reduction of HAuCl_4 solution using aqueous HS

leaf extract through a modified bio-green approach²⁴. Mishra *et al.* earlier synthesized gold nanoparticles using highly concentrated stem and leaf extracts of HS and showed that these nanoparticles were moderate to highly toxic to 293 as well as U87 glioblastoma cell lines, respectively even at very low dose (2.5 ng/mL). This could be attributed to the presence of HS extract containing toxic phytochemicals (e.g. protocatechuic acid, delphinidin-3-sambubioside etc.) on the surface of nanoparticles at higher concentration. The authors also proposed that the cytotoxicity might be due to the synergistic effect of plant extract and gold nanoparticles. It is highly essential for any nanoparticle/biomaterial/drug to be non-toxic for its different biomedical applications. Therefore, to obtain biocompatible gold nanomaterials, we have synthesized AuHS nanoparticles in a modified way employing very diluted HS leaf extract, so that the corresponding phytochemicals content become optimum for the reduction of H₂AuCl₄ as well as stabilization of nanoparticles, without exerting any nanomaterials mediated toxic effect even at higher doses (µg/mL range). In brief, HS extract (200–400 µL) was drop wisely added to the solution of H₂AuCl₄ (200 µL, 10⁻² M), keeping the total volume of the reaction mixture fixed at 5 mL and stirred it for overnight using a magnetic stirrer under an ambient condition to obtain the red colour AuHS nanoparticles. The as-synthesized nanoparticles were designated as AuHS-200, AuHS-300 and AuHS-400 where the numerical value indicated the volume of HS extract (in µL) used for their synthesis. The method for the formation of gold nanoparticles using the leaf extract is environmental-friendly and cost-effective compared to the conventional chemical methods. The as-synthesized nanoparticles were purified by removing the unreacted gold ions and HS extract through ultracentrifugation and the loose pellet was used for different characterizations as well as biological studies to avoid any unwanted toxic effect.

Characterizations of AuHS nanoparticles

The as-synthesized AuHS nanoparticles were thoroughly characterized employing different physico-

chemical techniques. The loose pellet (intense red) of AuHS nanoparticles were collected after centrifugation of 20 mL reaction mixture at 15,000 rpm, 20 °C for 45 min using an ultracentrifuge machine (Thermo Scientific, Sorvall-WX ultra 100) and stored at 4 °C for characterizations as well as other experimental use.

UV-Visible spectroscopy

The absorbance of as-synthesized AuHS-200, AuHS-300, AuHS-400 nanoparticles as well as HS extract was measured using UV-Visible spectroscopy (JASCO spectrophotometer) using quartz cuvette.

Dynamic light scattering (DLS)

DLS is a technique to determine the size and surface charge of nanoparticles/drug molecules. The pellets of as-synthesized AuHS-200, AuHS-300 and AuHS-400 nanoparticles (10 µL) were mixed with 990 µL of MiliQ water and the solutions were analyzed using a DLS instrument (Anton Paar) to determine the size and zeta-potential (surface charge) of nanoparticles.

X-Ray diffraction (XRD)

AuHS-400 pellet was coated on a glass slide and after evaporation of the solvent it was submitted for XRD analysis. The phase purity and crystalline nature of AuHS nanoparticles was determined employing X-ray diffractometer (Bruker AXS D8 Advance) with CuKα λ = 1.5406 Å radiation.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

TEM study was carried out to measure the size and morphology of the as-synthesized AuHS-400 nanoparticles obtained after 24 h of reaction condition. The loose pellet of nanoparticles was diluted in MiliQ water (1 : 3 ratio) and a drop of it was poured on the carbon grid followed by the evaporation of solvent. The measurement of size and morphology was evaluated using TEM (FEI Tecnai F12; Philips Electron Optics, Holland; operating condition 100 kV). The selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern was also obtained using the microscope.

Fourier transformed infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR)

FT-IR was used to determine the functional groups present in HS extract as well as AuHS-400 nanoparticles. The HS leaf extract and loose pellet of nanoparticles were drop-casted on the glass slides, dried at room temperature and submitted for FT-IR analysis employing Thermo Nicolet Nexus spectrometer with resolution of 4 cm^{-1} on KBr pellets.

X-Ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)

The surface property of the AuHS-400 nanoparticles was determined through XPS analysis. A glass slide was coated with the loose pellet of nanoparticles and submitted for XPS after evaporating the solvent. The instrument is relied on a KRATOS AXIS 165 with a dual anode (Mg and Al) apparatus employing Mg $K\alpha$ anode.

In vitro stability studies

To check the stability of the AuHS-400 nanoparticles in various solutions (e.g. H_2O , 5% NaCl, 10% NaCl, DPBS and buffer solutions of pH 6–8), 200 μL nanoparticles were incubated with each solution (1800 μL) for different time points (24 h, 7 days and 14 days) and measured their absorbance using UV-Visible spectroscopy to evaluate their change in λ_{max} .

Conjugation of DOX with AuHS nanoparticles and evaluation of % binding of DOX

DOX (100 μL ; 1 mg/mL) was drop wisely poured into the as-synthesized AuHS-400 nanoparticles (20 mL) and stirred for 2 h at room temperature to prepare AuHS-DOX drug delivery system (DDS). AuHS-DOX was then centrifuged at 15,000 rpm, 20 °C for 45 min to obtain AuHS-DOX pellet that was used for different experiments. The % attachment of DOX in AuHS-DOX DDS was calculated taking the supernatant of AuHS-DOX (as unknown) using spectrofluorimetry technique [$\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 480\text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 600\text{ nm}$ for DOX], after making a standard curve of DOX (0.125–5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) using supernatant of AuHS-400 nanoparticles.

Cell culture studies

Different normal cells (CHO and EA.hy926) as well as cancer cells (HCT-15, HeLa, PC3 and A549) were cultured in DMEM media supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 0.01% antibiotics (penicillin, streptomycin, kanamycin and ciprofloxacin) in a humidified 5% CO_2 incubator at 37 °C for all *in vitro* experiments. HS, AuHS-400 and AuHS-DOX were kept under UV light for 15 min prior to any *in vitro* experiment.

Cell viability assay

Cell viability assay was carried out employing MTT reagent following our earlier literature^{25,26}. Initially, 1×10^4 cells/well (non-cancerous : EA.hy926 and CHO; cancerous : HCT-15, HeLa, PC3 and A549) were seeded in 96-well plate and kept for 24 h in 37 °C incubator. The cells were incubated with HS extract (0.5–5 μL) and AuHS-400 pellet (0.5–5 μL) for 24 h and 48 h for normal cells and cancer cells, respectively to check their cell viability. Additionally, HCT-15, HeLa and PC3 cells were further incubated with AuHS-DOX pellet (0.03–0.25 μM w.r.to DOX), AuHS-400 pellet (0.03–0.25 μM w.r.to DOX) and free DOX (0.03–0.25 μM) for 48 h to assess the therapeutic efficacy of the DDS. After the incubation periods, 100 μL MTT solution (0.5 mg/mL) was added to each well and the plate was kept at 37 °C for 4 h. The media in each well was replaced by freshly prepared 100 μL of DMSO : MeOH solution (1 : 1, v/v) and absorbance was measured at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 570\text{ nm}$ using multimode reader.

Confocal microscopy for cellular uptake study

To check the intracellular uptake, 1×10^5 HCT-15 cells were grown on embedded cover slips in each well of 6-well culture dishes for 24 h. The cells were incubated with AuHS-DOX pellet (0.12 μM w.r.to DOX), AuHS-400 pellet (0.12 μM w.r.to DOX) and free DOX (0.12 μM) for 6 h. The cells were thoroughly washed with DPBS and fixed with 3.7% formaldehyde solution for 10 min. After washing with DPBS, the cover slips containing cells were mounted

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using DAPI vectashield on glass slides and observed under confocal microscope (laser used, 404.2, 561 nm in Nikon Ti Eclipse Confocal Microscope)²⁷.

CEA assay

CEA assay was carried out with AuHS-400 nanoparticles following our earlier literature^{25,26,28}. Before four days of experimental study, fertilized chicken eggs were incubated at egg incubator (~70% humidity, 37 °C). On the experimental day, a small window was carefully created on the top of the egg cell using a forcep and AuHS-400 pellet (5 µL) was gently administered on the blood vessels area of chicken embryo. Finally, images were captured at 0 h and 4 h post-treatments using an LEICA camera (LEICA MC120-HD) attached to a LEICA stereomicroscope (LEICA S8AP0) at 10 megapixel magnifications.

Results and discussion

The bio-green synthesis of AuHS nanoparticles using aqueous HS leaf extract (acting as a reducing agent) was carried out under ambient conditions. To obtain the desired stable AuHS nanoparticles a series of reactions were performed using different amount (200–400 µL) of leaf extract as mentioned in Table 1. Expt. No. #3 in Table 1 takes minimum time (45 min) for the appearance of red coloration (generation of gold nanoparticles), indicating this reaction condition (HS extract : 400 µL) as the optimized one. The result also shows that the rate of the reaction (in terms of appearance of red coloration) is faster with increasing concentration of HS extract. The as-synthesized nanoparticles were characterized employing sev-

eral analytical techniques and used for different *in vitro* and *in vivo* assays. The overall synthesis and biological applications of AuHS nanoparticles are described in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. Overall schematic diagram for synthesis, characterization of biocompatible AuHS nanoparticles and their application as delivery vehicle for cancer therapy.

UV-Visible spectroscopy

The absorbance of the as-synthesized AuHS-200, AuHS-300 and AuHS-400 nanoparticles using different concentration of HS extract was measured using UV-Visible spectroscopy. Fig. 1A reveals that surface plasmon resonance (SPR) bands of these nanoparticles after 24 h of reaction appeared at $\lambda_{\max} \sim 535\text{--}540$ nm, indicating the formation of gold nanoparticles. The absorbance intensity of nanoparticles was enhanced with increasing concentration of HS extract used for their synthesis. The maximum absorbance was observed for AuHS-400 nanoparticles having ruby red color (inset picture of Fig. 1A), suggesting their higher stability compared to AuHS-200 and AuHS-300 nanoparticles. Moreover, the appearance of red coloration for AuHS-400 nanoparticles came in a shorter time in comparison with that of AuHS-200 and AuHS-300 nanoparticles (Table 1). Based on these factors of higher stability and higher

Table 1. Reaction conditions for the synthesis of gold nanoparticles (AuHS) using *Hibiscus sabdariffa* (HS) plant leaf extract

Expt. No.	HS extract (µL)	HAuCl ₄ (µL)	Water (mL)	Total volume (mL)	Time ^a (min)
1.	200	200	4.6	5	85
2.	300	200	4.5	5	60
3.	400	200	4.4	5	45

^aTime required to observe the red coloration indicating the formation of AuHS.

rate of reaction AuHS-400 nanoparticles were considered as the optimized gold nanoparticles for further studies (thorough characterizations and biological experiments).

We have also measured the time dependent absorbance of optimized AuHS-400 nanoparticles (generally termed as AuHS nanoparticles) through UV-Visible spectroscopy (Fig. 1B). The absorbance intensity of nanoparticles was found to increase in a time dependant manner up to 24 h. However, after 48 h of reaction the absorbance intensity of nanoparticles falls slightly. Therefore, 24 h reaction time point was selected as optimized condition to synthesize AuHS-400 nanoparticles for their detailed characterizations and biological studies.

Fig. 1. (A) UV-Visible spectra of AuHS nanoparticles using different volumes (200–400 μL) of HS extract after 24 h of reaction. The numerical values denote the corresponding volume of HS extract used in μL . The inset optical pictures indicate the colors of as-synthesized : (a) AuHS-200, (b) AuHS-300 and (c) AuHS-400 nanoparticles as well as (d) HS extract. (B) Time dependent UV-Visible spectra of optimized AuHS-400 nanoparticles.

Dynamic light scattering (DLS)

DLS was employed to determine the size and zeta potential (ξ) of as-synthesized nanoparticles. The hydrodynamic diameter was found to be AuHS-200, AuHS-300 and AuHS-400 nanoparticles 294.2, 350.11, 174.85 nm, respectively (Fig. 2a-c). The zeta potential provides an essential idea regarding the surface charge and stability of nanoparticles²². DLS study exhibits the negative zeta potential/surface charge of AuHS-200 (-6.7 ± 0.3 mV), AuHS-300 (-4.6 ± 0.3 mV) and AuHS-400 (-6.5 ± 0.3 mV) nanoparticles (Fig. 2d-f), suggesting the long term stability and dispersity of nanoparticles without any aggregation in solution, due to negative-negative repulsive force.

X-Ray diffraction (XRD) analysis and transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

XRD analysis was employed to analyze the crystal structure of as-synthesized AuHS nanoparticles. The diffraction peaks appeared at hkl planes (111), (200), (220) and (311) are consistent with standard data files having JCPDS card no : 04-0784 (Fig. 3a)²⁹. As per the Bragg's reflections, AuHS nanoparticles are distinctly indexed to FCC (face centered cubic) crystal structure. The absence of extra peak in X-ray diffraction pattern indicates the high purity of crystalline AuHS nanoparticles. The inset picture of Fig. 3a represents the SAED pattern of AuHS nanoparticles indicating their face centered cubic (FCC) crystal structure which corroborate with the XRD result.

In order to comprehend the size and morphology of the synthesized AuHS nanoparticles, TEM analysis was employed. Fig. 3b represents the TEM image exhibiting that AuHS nanoparticles consisted of mostly spherical shaped particles (diameter : ~ 5 –30 nm) as well as some triangle particles. The generation of the larger triangle particles might be the result of slow growth process due to weak reducing agents present in HS extract³⁰.

Fourier transformed infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR)

To understand the formation of AuHS nanoparticles using HS leaf extract, FT-IR analysis was carried

Fig. 2. DLS analysis for the measurement of size and zeta potential of as-synthesized nanoparticles. Size : (a) AuHS-200, (b) AuHS-300 and (c) AuHS-400 nanoparticles; Zeta potential : (d) AuHS-200, (e) AuHS-300 and (f) AuHS-400 nanoparticles.

out. Fig. 4 exhibits various peaks of HS extract and AuHS nanoparticles, which could be attributed to the different phytochemicals present in these systems. The peak at 3430.21 cm^{-1} for HS extract can be designated to -OH stretching, which was shifted to lower frequency (3424.39 cm^{-1}) and became sharper for AuHS nanoparticles. This result indicates the major role of polyphenolic/alcoholic compound for the reduction of HAuCl_4 to form AuHS nanoparticles^{17,31}. The peak appeared at 2931.29 cm^{-1} for HS corresponds to the -C-H stretching of aliphatic group which

was also shifted to 2919.20 cm^{-1} for AuHS nanoparticles³². The three peaks at 1795.53 , 1745.2 , 1629.79 cm^{-1} could be assigned for keto group of acid anhydride, ester and amide I compounds, respectively present in HS extract and all of the corresponding peaks (1784.45 , 1723.87 , 1626.25 cm^{-1}) are also present in AuHS nanoparticles, suggesting the attachment of these phytochemicals on the surface of nanoparticles for their stabilization³³. While, the peaks appeared at 1407.97 cm^{-1} (HS) and 1403.17 cm^{-1} (AuHS) could be referred to the -NH group in

Fig. 3. (a) X-Ray diffraction pattern of as-synthesized AuHS nanoparticles indicating the FCC crystalline structure of nanoparticles. The inset figure represents the SAED pattern of the nanoparticles. (b) TEM image of biosynthesized AuHS nanoparticles suggesting their spherical morphology.

protein amide linkages³⁴, peaks observed at 1096.55 cm^{-1} (HS) and 1020.32 cm^{-1} might be assigned to the -C-N stretching of aliphatic amines. The peaks appeared at 529.41 and 522.51 cm^{-1} for HS and for AuHS, respectively might be designated to the C-H bending vibrations³⁵. The FT-IR analysis altogether suggests that different phytochemicals such as phenolic/alcoholic compounds, amides, proteins etc. present in HS extract could play an important role for the formation as well as stabilization of AuHS nanoparticles.

Fig. 4. FT-IR of HS extract and as-synthesized AuHS nanoparticles indicating the role of different components of plant leaf extract for the synthesis of AuHS nanoparticles.

X-Ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)

XPS analysis was employed to understand the surface property of the synthesized AuHS nanoparticles. Fig. 5 exhibits the binding energy (BE) peak at 87.8 eV for [Au(4f)], indicating the presence of Au^0 in AuHS nanoparticles. The other peaks at 285 eV, 400 eV and 533 eV can be assigned to [C(1s)], [N(1s)] and [O(1s)], respectively.

Fig. 5. XPS analysis of as-synthesized AuHS nanoparticles.

In vitro stability studies of AuHS nanoparticles

The stability of the nanoparticles is one of the fundamental criteria for their biological applications which compel us to perform *in vitro* stability studies of as-synthesized AuHS nanoparticles in different physiological buffer (pH 6, 7 and 8) and other solutions (H₂O, 5% NaCl, 10% NaCl and DPBS)^{22,36}. The result demonstrated only a slight change in plasmon wavelength (λ_{max}) and plasmon bandwidth ($\Delta\lambda$) was <5 nm for AuHS nanoparticles up to 14 days, indicating their high *in vitro* stability in those solutions (Fig. 6). It could be speculated that different proteins, carbohydrates, phenolic compounds *etc.* present in HS extract might support the higher stability of AuHS nanoparticles²⁹.

Fig. 6. *In vitro* stability studies of AuHS nanoparticles in different buffer and other solutions.

Cell viability assay

The cell viability assay using MTT reagent is one of the fundamental assays for any nanoparticle/drug prior to its biomedical applications³⁷. Therefore, cell viability assay of AuHS nanoparticles was performed in different non-cancerous cells (EA.hy926 : Fig. 7a and CHO : Fig. 7b) as well as cancerous cells (HCT-15 : Fig. 8a, HeLa : Fig. 8b, PC3 : Fig. 8c and A549 : Fig. 8d). The result reveals that AuHS nanoparticles treatment (0.5–5 μL) did not affect the viability of both these normal and cancer cell lines, suggesting their biocompatible nature. Similar, re-

Fig. 7. *In vitro* cell viability assay in different normal cells [(a) EA.hy926 and (b) CHO]. The result exhibits the biocompatible nature of HS extract (0.5–5 μL ; 24 h) and AuHS nanoparticles (0.5–5 μL ; 24 h). The numerical values indicate the volume in μL .

sults was also observed with the treatment of aqueous HS leaf extract. Prior to the treatment of AuHS nanoparticles, the gold concentration of pellet was found to be 1.77 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$, as calculated employing ICP-OES technique. Therefore, 0.5, 1, 2.5 and 5 μL AuHS nanoparticles pellet treatments for cell viability assay correspond to gold concentrations of 8.85, 17.7, 44.25 and 88.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, respectively.

CEA assay

To confirm the biocompatibility of AuHS nanoparticles, *in vivo* CEA assay was further employed. Fig. 9 exhibits that AuHS treatment did not affect the vascular sprouting in chick embryo in terms of blood vessel length, junction and size even after 4 h of incubation period as compared to untreated control experiments, indicating the biocompatibility of nanoparticles. This result corroborates with the cell viability data, suggesting the feasibility of bio-

compatible AuHS nanoparticles for different biomedical applications.

Fig. 8. *In vitro* cell viability assay in different cancer cells [(a) HCT-15, (b) HeLa, (c) PC3 and (d) A549]. The result exhibits the biocompatibility of both the HS extract (0.5–5 μL ; 24 h) and AuHS nanoparticles (0.5–5 μL ; 24 h). The numerical values indicate the volume in μL .

Design of AuHS-DOX and quantification of % binding of DOX

Considering the biocompatible nature, we have designed an AuHS nanoparticles based DDS (AuHS-DOX), containing DOX as an FDA approved anti-cancer drug and hypothesized that AuHS nanoparticles could be an effective delivery vehicles for the treatment of cancers. Prior to investigate the therapeutic efficacy of the DDS, it was highly essential to check the % attachment of DOX in AuHS-DOX DDS. The spectrofluorimetry analysis using supernatant of AuHS-DOX and standard curve of pristine DOX (Fig. 10) reveals that % binding of DOX in the DDS was $\sim 41\%$. It seems that the attachment of DOX with AuHS nanoparticles might be due to the weak electrostatic attraction, as these nanoparticles possess negative surface charge while DOX has positive zeta potential according to earlier literature^{17,38,39}.

Therapeutic efficacy of AuHS-DOX DDS

To confirm our hypothesis that AuHS could be an effective delivery vehicle of DOX for cancer treat-

Fig. 9. *In vivo* CEA assay employing AuHS nanoparticles (5 μL , 4 h). The result illustrates that AuHS nanoparticles did not affect the blood vessel growth in terms of vessel length, junction and size, supporting their biocompatible nature.

Fig. 10. Standard curve of doxorubicin (DOX) for evaluation of % binding of DOX in AuHS-DOX DDS using spectrofluorimetry technique.

ment, cell viability assay was again performed employing the DDS in different cancer cells (HCT-15 : Fig. 11a, HeLa : Fig. 11b and PC-3 : Fig. 11c). The result exhibits that the administration of AuHS-DOX significantly inhibited the cancer cell proliferation compared to pristine DOX in a dose dependent manner irrespective of cancer cell line, suggesting the therapeutic potential of the DDS. Considering the biocompatible nature of AuHS nanoparticles and the better antiproliferative effect of AuHS-DOX to cancer cells, it could be speculated that the DDS could be useful for the anticancer therapy in forthcoming future.

Cellular uptake studies using confocal microscopy

The higher therapeutic potential of DDS compared to free drug might often be due to the better cellular uptake of the DDS⁴⁰. To confirm this fact, confocal microscopy was employed for comprehending the uptake of AuHS-DOX in HCT-15 cells in terms of fluorescence intensity of DOX, present in the DDS. Fig. 12 and Fig. 13 reveals that untreated control cells and cell treated with AuHS nanoparticles did not exhibit any fluorescence. However, cells incubated with AuHS-DOX showed red fluorescence with higher intensity as compared to cells treated with free DOX,

Fig. 11. Therapeutic potential of AuHS-DOX DDS in different cancer cells [(a) HCT-15, (b) HeLa and (c) PC3]. The result exhibits that AuHS-DOX (0.03–0.25 µM w.r.to DOX; 48 h) treatment significantly inhibits the proliferation of cancer cells as compared to free DOX (0.03–0.25 µM; 48 h) in a dose dependent manner.

indicating the better cellular uptake of the DDS than that of pristine drug. The enhanced uptake of AuHS-DOX compared to free DOX might be due to the EPR effect in cancer cells⁴¹. The results altogether corroborate with the better anti-proliferative efficacy of AuHS-DOX compared to free DOX to cancer cells.

Plausible mechanism for synthesis of AuHS nanoparticles

There are numerous reports for the synthesis of gold nanoparticles using different plant extracts. However, precise mechanism for the fabrication of gold nanoparticles using this strategy still remains ambiguous. As per the earlier literature, plant extract often

Fig. 12. Cellular uptake study in HCT-15 cells using confocal microscope with 40x objective with zoom-2.331. The result reveals the enhanced uptake of DOX present in AuHS-DOX (0.12 μM w.r.to DOX) as compared to free DOX (0.12 μM) at same treatment dose. Scale bar : 10 μm .

augments the reduction of HAuCl_4 for the formation as well as stabilization of gold nanoparticles^{17,22,30,42}. In the present study, we have synthesized AuHS nanoparticles using aqueous HS leaf extract, which served as both reducing and stabilizing agent. HS contains several polyphenolic/alcoholic compounds (e.g. ellagic acids, catechin, hydroxycitric acid, β -sitosterol- β -D-galactoside etc.), amide/amine compounds, aromatic ketones, aldehydes etc. which might be responsible for the reduction of Au^{3+} (HAuCl_4) to Au^0 (AuHS : gold nanoparticles) as well as their stabilization⁴³⁻⁴⁶. The standard reduction potential for $\text{Au}^{3+}/\text{Au}^0$ system ($E^0 \text{Au}^{3+}/\text{Au}^0$) is 1.50 eV which is higher compared to that of acid/aldehyde, aldehyde/alcohol system ($E^0 \text{ROH}/\text{RCO}/\text{RCHO}$: 0.80 eV) and so polyphenolic/alcoholic phytochemicals present in HS extract could easily augment the reduction of HAuCl_4 (Au^{3+}) to AuHS nanoparticles

Fig. 13. Cellular uptake study in HCT-15 cells using confocal microscope with 40x objective (without any zooming). The result reveals the enhanced uptake of DOX present in AuHS-DOX (0.12 μM w.r.to DOX) as compared to free DOX (0.12 μM) at same treatment dose. Scale bar : 50 μm .

(Au^0)⁴⁷. Moreover, Newman *et al.* demonstrated the formation of gold nanoparticles through the reduction of the HAuCl_4 to elemental gold (Au^0) by amine/amide compounds present in the plant extract. This redox reaction might take place through an electron transfer mechanism between amine to the metal ion⁴⁶. Earlier reports also suggested that low (10–22 kDa) as well as high molecular weight proteins (100–200 kDa) present in leaf extract might be one of the reason of the reducing properties of the extract^{17,29}. However, the reducing potential of these proteins may vary depending on the nature of the plant. FT-IR analysis also supports that HS extract possess different phytochemicals (e.g. polyphenol compounds, alcohols, amines etc.) which are responsible for the synthesis and stabilization of AuHS nanoparticles. Scheme 2 represents the overall mechanism for the synthesis and stabilization of AuHS nanoparticles using HS leaf extract.

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Scheme 2. The plausible mechanism for the generation and stabilization of AuHS nanoparticles using *Hibiscus sabdariffa* plant extract.

Conclusions

Through the use of a bio-green method, gold nanoparticles (AuHS) were fabricated under an ambient conditions using HS leaf extract, which acts as a reducing as well as stabilizing agent. The as-synthesized AuHS nanoparticles were characterized by several analytical methods. AuHS nanoparticles were found to be stable in different solutions/physiological buffers indicating their feasibility for biological applications. Cell viability assay and CEA assay indicate the biocompatible nature of AuHS nanoparticles. Considering the biocompatibility of AuHS nanoparticles, AuHS-DOX DDS was designed where AuHS nanoparticles act as delivery vehicle and DOX as an FDA approved anti-cancer drug. The administration of the DDS exhibited more inhibition of cancer cell proliferation compared to free DOX, suggesting the efficacy of the DDS. Additionally, confocal microscopy study reveals the enhanced cellular uptake of AuHS-DOX DDS compared to free DOX, supporting the therapeutic potential of the DDS. This study provides the basis for the development of other biocompatible gold nanoparticles that might be used for effective drug delivery vehicle for the treatment of cancers in near future.

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